

Short communication

Differentiation of two closely related species of the genus *Empoasca* (Hem.: Cicadellidae)

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چکیده

پیش‌تر، گونه‌ای زنجبرک از مزارع چغندرقد استان اصفهان به اشتباه به نام *Empoasca decipiens* (Paoli) گزارش شده است که در این نوشتار نام صحیح آن به صورت *Empoasca meridiana* Zachvatkin اعلام می‌گردد. گونه‌ی اخیر دارای سینونیم شناخته‌تری به نام *Empoasca punjabensis* Singh-Pruthi می‌باشد. گونه‌های آسیایی خویشاوند گونه‌ی *E. decipiens*، براساس شکل پیگوفر (pygofer) ژنیتالیای نر از هم تفکیک می‌گردند، به‌طوری‌که پیگوفر در گونه‌ی *E. meridiana* دوکی‌شکل ولی در گونه‌ی *E. decipiens* عدسی‌شکل می‌باشد.

During the faunistic studies on Auchenorrhyncha (Hemiptera) of sugarbeet fields in Isfahan province (Iran) between 1995 and 1997, specimens of genus *Empoasca* Walsh (Cicadellidae: Typhlocybinae: Empoascini) belonging to the group species *Empoasca decipiens* were collected. Based on reliable literature (Ribaut, 1936; Emeljanov, 1967; LeQuesne & Payne, 1981), the collected specimens were then determined as *Empoasca decipiens* (Paoli) (Karimzadeh, 1997; Karimzadeh *et al.*, 1998). However, this determination was somewhat controversial because of the earlier report of *Empoasca meridiana* Zachvatkin from the same region (Kheyri & Alimoradi, 1968). Due to lack of data on discrimination of the two mentioned species and inaccessibility of the original description of latter species the problem remained unsolved.

Here, this is documented that the earlier reports on *E. decipiens* from Isfahan's sugarbeet fields (Karimzadeh, 1997; Karimzadeh *et al.*, 1998) have just been misidentifications of *E. meridiana*. It is now clear that all specimens of *Empoasca* sp. collected from Isfahan's sugarbeet fields were *E. meridiana*, which has a more known synonym, *Empoasca punjabensis* Singh-Pruthi (Dworakowska, 1973; Sohi & Dworakowska, 1983; Sohi & Mann, 1987). These two closely related species are distinguished based on the pygofer process of male genitalia, which is fusiform in *E. meridiana* while it is lentiform in *E. decipiens*. In both species, the curvature of the pygofer process faces almost perfectly compared with other related species in that it considerably shifts apart (fig. 1).

Figure 1. The pygofer process of male genitalia in Asiatic species related to *E. decipiens*. (a) *E. turanica*, (b) *E. pteridis*, (c) *E. meridiana*, (d) *E. decipiens*, (e) *E. affinis*.

References

- Dworakowska, I.** (1973) *Bagoidea ryfa* (Mel.) and some other Empoascini (Auchenorrhyncha, Cicadellidae). *Bulletin de l'Academie Polonaise des Sciences, Serie des Sciences Biologiques* 21, 49-58.
- Emeljanov, A. F.** (1967) Suborder Cicadinea (Auchenorrhyncha). pp. 421-551 in Bei-Bienko, G. Y. (Ed.) *Keys to the insects of the European USSR, I. Apterygota, Palaeoptera, Hemimetabola*. 1214 pp. Smithsonian Institution, National Science Foundation.
- Karimzadeh, J.** (1997) Studies on Auchenorrhyncha (Homoptera) fauna of sugarbeet fields in Isfahan province. M. Sc. Thesis. 162 pp. University of Tehran. [In Persian].
- Karimzadeh, J., Kharazi-Pakdel, A. & Kheyri, M.** (1998) Leafhopper and planthopper (Homoptera, Auchenorrhyncha) fauna of sugarbeet fields in Isfahan province. *Proceedings of the 13th Iranian Plant Protection Congress, Vol. 1, Pests*, 69.

- Kheyri, M. & Alimoradi, A.** (1968) *The leafhoppers of sugarbeet in Iran and their roles in transmitting the curly-top viral disease*. 50 pp. Sugarbeet Seed Institute. [In Persian].
- LeQuesne, W. J. & Payne, K. R.** (1981) *Cicadellidae (Typhlocybinae) with a check list of the British Auchenorrhyncha (Hemiptera, Homoptera)*. *Handbooks for the identification of British insects*, 2 (2c). 95 pp. Royal Entomological Society of London.
- Ribaut, H.** (1936) Homoptères Auchenorrhynques (I. Typhlocybidae). *Faune de France* 31, 1-231.
- Sohi, A. S. & Dworakowska, I.** (1983) A review of the Indian Typhlocybinae (Homoptera, Cicadellidae) from India. *Oriental Insects* 17, 159-213.
- Sohi, A. S. & Mann, J. S.** (1987) Illustrated key for identification of Indian species of Emposcini (Cicadellidae, Typhlocybinae). *Proceedings of the 6th Auchenorrhyncha Meeting*, 213-230. University of Turin Press.

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